

An Innovation Searching for Analyzing the Chinese Part Central Provinces GDP & the Israel & Top Chinese Cities GDP Status Sustainably

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ABSTRACT: The high-tech product is able to increase the GDP ratio gradually according to developing situation presently. It is to believe that the ratio will raise a certain one in near future because it has high-knowledge & high-science factors within knowing it to producing it from the transfer of laboratory to factory. So that the new product enables us to exhibit in its market after it was made in a factory continuously through using our scientist and engineers' behaviour positively. We must encourage the high-tech proceeding engineers etc. who will transform the idea stimulus into the searching behaviour in lab with other researchers through acquiring a certain project from the funding so as to erect the experience and knowledge after several years that makes the sample into product entering current market to complete the receiving the order and transiting the cuisine to customers. That will be said that automatic changing to artificial intelligence one in order to promote the time and efficiency at all through the huge change said, "let it do" changed to "it can do". We should continuously enhance its function and upgrade it & make its stability that means it can undergo a long time to serve as a like humanoid

robot that may sometimes be exhibited in our canteen as an automatic and artificial intelligence one to save some money while promoting its quality and efficiency concept. Thereby, the GDP increasement will coordinate the infrastructure and industrial innovation, and the latter will include high-technique product making ones. We may continually improve our capacity to make a new high-level product for the sake of promoting our industrial development with a certain value each year. The other one will be foreign trade exportation that may help us earn the foreign money to use in later urgent time. So, the industry, learning, research & usefulness etc. procedures will be boosting that combines into university, institution, factory & office four aspects cooperative spirits and culture for the sake of building a good future.

Keywords: *innovation; the Chinese Part Central Provinces GDP; the Israel & Top Chinese Cities GDP; analyzing; searching*

1. Introduction

The nations & regions GDP will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statisti c with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decrease ment through that y-y value for a certain period. Thereby, the detail discussion will include in the following aspects. The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence), ocean source space exploration

nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation. [1~15]

2. Discussions

In this paper the detail GDP value is going to be discussed as above parts through comparing the various regions for the sake of enhancing corresponding tactic in next year and futural several years. Eventually the regional GDP will be compared with their variation and then confidently make a strategic plan for concluding the past years and erecting new target that we pay much attention to raise our predicting value all the time. It is clarified that with regulating our aim the good achievement will be finishing in future that makes us to be more confident year by year for the sake of realizing the plan at present and in certain future. On the other side, we should learn and develop relevant project and subject to reveal the core one after their phenomena. Then we master that technique to apply to that kind of substance making ability through the engineers and scientists transformed to the R & D (research & development) department in makers. Therein, a sample will change into launch

product by us to search for which may bring out new functional precise and quick responding to our request up to now. We should go on developing our similar functional equipment continually.

2.1 Chinese part central provinces GDP Changes

The Chinese part central provinces GDP changes in 1964 might show 0.6 & 0.5 billion yuan Anhui~Jiangxi respectively to express their modest economy strength in Figure 1. The y-y value might indicate 2.5% & 12% by them respectively showed the Jiangxi rapider steps.

Figure 1. The Chinese part central provinces GDP changes [1]

2.2 Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison

The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP changes in 1996 might show 121 & 100 billion yuan Tianjin~Wuxi respectively to express their modest economy strength in Figure 2. The y-y value might indicate 19% & 25% by Suzhou~Wuxi cities respectively showed their rapider steps. In contrast the Shenzhen one attained 36% exhibiting “Shenzhen speed” with highest 121 billion yuan GDP.

Figure 2. The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison. [2]

At the same time, the Israel & top Chinese cities GDP changes in 1996 might show 121-&-100-billion-yuan Israel~Shanghai respectively to express their forwards economy strength in Figure 3. The y-y value might indicate 12% & 25% by them cities respectively showed their rapider steps.

Figure 3. The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison. [2]

On the other hand, the Israel & top Chinese cities GDP changes in 1996 might show 121-&-100-billion-yuan Beijing & Guangzhou cities respectively to express their high economy strength in Figure 4. The y-y value might indicate 28% & 24% by them cities respectively showed their rapider steps.

Figure 4. The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison. [2]

The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison might show 202~996 billion yuan by Guangzhou~Israel ones respectively to record their forwards steps in 1998 in light of Figure 5. In contrast, the Shanghai & Beijing cities followed the Israel occupy the second~third position.

Figure 5. The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison. [2]

At the same time, the Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison might show 118~167 billion yuan by Hangzhou~Shenzhen ones respectively to record their forwards steps in 1998 in light of Figure 6. In contrast, the Chongqing, Tianjin & Suzhou cities followed the Shenzhen occupy the second~forth position.

Figure 6. The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison. [2]

In short, we need to continue to search those cutting-edge-fields through our experts and scientists because those aspects may be proceeded sustainably special in low-contamination non fossil fuel like wind energy photovoltaic energy hydraulic one nuclear reacting-pile one. So we need a lot of engineers & scholars etc. participating cooperatively and satisfy the producing learning searching & usefulness series of industrial procedures to invest and push into market meeting consumers demands. There will be still big resilient space to wield our imagination and research capacity to publish the relevant achievement in famous journals so as to arouse the basis & application aspects research together for alleviating the cause matters. We should continue to search and develop the low-carbon energy base status and application to futural huge requirement electricity for example the chargeable battery technique etc.

reserved energy stations which increases from several years gradually meeting the electrical vehicle hybrid vehicle even small motorcycles.

3. Conclusions

The high-tech product is able to increase the GDP ratio gradually according to developing situation presently. It is to believe that the ratio will raise a certain one in near future because it has high-knowledge & high-science factor within knowing it to producing it from the transfer of laboratory to factory. So that the new product enables to exhibit in its market after it was made in a factory continuously through using our scientist and engineers behaviour positively. We must encourage the high-tech proceeding engineers etc. who will transform the idea stimulus into the searching behaviour in lab with other researchers through acquiring a certain project from the funding so as to erect the experience and knowledge after several years that makes the sample into product entering current market to complete the receiving the order and transiting the cuisine to customers. That will be said that automatic changing to artificial intelligence one in order to promote the time and efficiency at all through the huge change said “let it do” changed to “it can do”. we should continuously enhance its function and upgrade it & make its stability that means it can undergo a long time to serve as a like humanoid robot that may sometimes exhibit in our canteen as an automatic and artificial intelligence one to save some money while promoting its quality and efficiency concept. Thereby, the GDP increasement will coordinate the infrastructure and industrial innovation, and the latter includes high-technique product making ones. We may continually improve our capacity to make a new high-level product for the sake of promoting our industrial development with a certain value each year. The other one will be foreign trade exportation that may help us earn the foreign money to use in later urgent time. So the industry, learning, research & usefulness etc. procedures will be boosting that combines into university, institution, factory & office four aspects cooperative spirits and culture for the sake of building a good future.

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Ethic Declarations

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest.

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